

The influence of location on the shaping of small-town functional structure in Poland

Jerzy Bański, Polish Academy of Sciences & Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce

Abstract

The aim of the work detailed here has been to assess the influence of the spatial locations of small towns on their functional structure. Relevant analysis involves 7 regions of Poland, with a total of 91 small towns representing two types of location category, i.e. within metropolitan areas or with a peripheral location. More specifically, research carried out used two means achieving functional classification, using either structural/hierarchical or morphological/functional analysis. Results emerged as confirming initial assumptions on the socio-economic functions small urban localities play as a reflection of their locations. In general, towns in metropolitan locations serve functions beyond purely local ones and display a specialised economic structure within which residential and industrial functions prevail. In turn, the functional structure of towns in peripheral locations emerges as highly diversified, with the role in supplying local functions also proving more significant in this case. Overall, the differences between the so-called metropolitan and peripheral small towns are seen to arise more from their level in the hierarchy than from economic structure as such.

Keywords

Small towns, functional structure, metropolitan areas, peripheries, Poland

Introduction

Small-sized urban localities (typically – though not always unproblematically – termed “small towns”) form a key element of a country’s settlement structure, given that they are engaged in the discharge of a series of key social and economic functions. It is for such reasons that they have been the subject of many academic studies (including in human geography). The main research axes have in fact been devoted to demographic issues; functional structure; or the relations pertaining with agglomeration-level centres on the one hand, and rural areas on the other (Dej et al., 2014; Duranton & Puga, 2005; Edwards et al., 2003; Heffner & Halama, 2012; Powe, 2013; Shucksmith et al., 2005; Van Leeuwen, 2010). A key role played by small towns obviously relates to the servicing of surrounding rural areas. The towns in question may provide various services to the community and public more widely (e.g. in administration, education and healthcare), may supply local firms and farms with (many of)

their goods and services, and may represent markets for local produce and products (Tacoli, 1998). The strength of linkages with surrounding rural areas (with which they create a system that helps direct local development) are what ensure a perception of the localities in question as transmission nodes in and for development policy, be that at national or regional level (Courtney et al., 2007; Najarsadeghi & Dorostkar, 2022; Zhao et al., 2023).

Today it is possible to observe increased functional diversity of small towns, inter alia in reflection of greater economic diversification of rural areas (Bogdański, 2021; Courtney et al., 2007; Hamdouch et al., 2017). In Poland's case, an important factor in shaping the structure of small towns has been the economic transformation following the collapse of the communist system. This gave rise to distinct change in the social and economic structure of small urban localities. On the one hand, there was a collapse and/or privatisation of what had hitherto been state-owned enterprises, while on the other numerous new ones of diverse branch structure came into being, though mostly of small size and in the private sector. Referring to the small towns in Poland's Silesia (Śląskie) Voivodeship, Zuzańska-Zyśko (2005) confirmed how the 1990s had yielded a dramatic increase in numbers of new enterprises in the towns servicing agricultural areas, even as the rate of growth in new business entities was far weaker when it came to the urban centres of specialised functions (e.g. mining or even tourism).

In general, the identification of main functions of towns is a process based around analysis of prevailing sector(s) of the economy, or else the roles attributable to different socio-economic features as towns develop. Elsasser (1998) for example distinguished between four basic functions of small urban localities, i.e. the supply-related, the residential, the labour market-related and the cultural. In turn, Ireland's National Spatial Strategy (DELG, 2000) identified 7 functions as follows: financial services, retail services, business services, social and administrative services, educational services, tourism and leisure services and agricultural services. Seven types of small or medium-sized urban centre were likewise distinguished in Switzerland (Meili & Mayer, 2017). Bearing in mind economic features and socio-economic dynamics, it was there possible to identify the functional types of residential economy towns, prospering residential economy towns, business-hub towns, knowledge-intensive towns, high-tech towns, low-tech towns and Alpine tourism towns. For its part, ESPON studies identify 5 functional categories in: 1) administration – at either local or regional level, 2) decision-making – with account here taken of localities that are the seats of the Boards of enterprises, 3) transport – as associated with the generation of transport links with other centres, 4) knowledge – given the activity of research institutions or various establishments operating in higher education, and 5) tourism – as a reflection of tourist-related and/or cultural activity (ESPON, 2007).

Differentiation in functional categories of small town reflects conditions arising out of history, natural environment, location in respect of key economic facilities and large urban centres, and socio-economic structure in surrounding rural areas. In this study, the author's

attention is mainly on the location of small town in relation to large(r) centres of development, and the ways in which functional structure is affected.

Having regard to the concept of the continuum considered to extend between centre and periphery, it is possible to draw distinctions between three main categories of location of small towns, i.e. 1) as satellite centres located in the zone of impact of large agglomerations and metropolises, 2) as towns constituting the traditional foci of the settlement system, and 3) as isolated centres located peripherally. A similar way of identifying urban localities was applied within the framework of the ESPON SMESTO Project (ESPON, 2006), which concerned towns in the vicinity of large agglomerations, neighbouring towns forming a network of linkages, and isolated towns.

A location-related criterion usually used to arrange small urban centres in some kind of order is time of travel to a more major centre (typically of regional or national rank). Such an assumption for example underpinned work done to classify towns in Scotland (Pateman 2010), with this making reference to the categories of accessible small towns, remote small towns and very remote small towns. On that basis it was reported that, location notwithstanding, each of the three categories of town was characterised by specific socio-economic functions. These defined functions were first and foremost seen to reflect the relationship between small towns and large centres of development, as well as the rural areas surrounding them, even as location is a pre-cause of differentiation of function. Thus, relationships between small towns and large economic centres when it comes to the functioning of the labour market (albeit largely as a reflection of locations vis-à-vis one another) form a basis upon which to distinguish 4 categories of small urban locality (Jones et al., 2009; Cox & Longlands, 2016). The first such relationship, described as “independent” is one whereby the small town features a strong labour market irrespective of the influence a more major (or main) centre is able to exert. Where this is not the case, we are dealing with relations of the “dependent” kind. In turn, in towns of the “isolated” type, the labour markets in small and large localities remain unconnected to one another, even as “interdependent”-type circumstances involve labour markets in the two categories of urban centre that are closely interlinked and interdependent in the true sense.

A dependence of functional structure on location has been demonstrated for towns in Wales (Wales Rural Observatory, 2007), the Czech Republic (Vaishar & Zapletalová, 2009), Poland (Bański et al., 2016) and Turkey (Montabone, 2013). Thus, for example, the three categories of small urban centre noted in the Moravian part of the Czech Republic were: 1) towns within the range of impact of large urban centres, 2) towns enjoying good access to larger cities, and 3) peripheral towns. It was noted how, in line with location, localities of the first type lost their central functions, those of the second type developed specific functions, and those located peripherally came to serve as centres for their own hinterlands. A similar situation applies to the small towns of east-central Poland's Mazovia region, it being noted

how the ones located peripherally in respect of the very large and key centre that is Warsaw discharge more functions and play a more important role for the rural areas around them than do analogous centres located in the vicinity of agglomerations (Bański et al., 2016).

In turn, the Turkish work referred to took account of economic structure, as well as degrees of independence of the city of Izmir, with this approach making it possible to identify 4 functional types of small urban centre, i.e. those: 1) with a prevalent residential function (located in close proximity to metropolises, 2) with a function associated with producing for the metropolis, 3) of an independent nature (e.g. serving as tourist towns), and 4) rural centres upholding the relations between rural areas and the metropolis (Montabone, 2013). That said, all of the small towns researched were under the influence of Izmir to a greater or lesser extent, even as they also played their part in encouraging its development.

While earlier considerations indeed stressed the key significance of location vis-à-vis a large city when it came to the shaping of towns' functional structure, it has also proved possible to identify other groups of factors. Thus, Satterthwaite and Tacoli (2003) were of the view that small urban localities support regional development in four ways, i.e. as centres of demand for agricultural output, as centres for the production and distribution of goods reaching surrounding rural areas, as local centres of employment, and as places attracting rural migrants. The suggestion is then that the precise role assumed depends on the specific context in which the town finds itself, and notably on: structure as regards land ownership, quality of transport and communications, and structural conditions operating at the international, national and local levels.

For his part, Lamprecht (2008) held that functional transformation acting upon industrial areas of small towns was a function of the land use that had once pertained in the area, accessibility (both as regards transport and less tangibly in terms of land ownership being fully regulated or not), as well as the subjective value of the actual land.

Against that background, the present study using the example of Poland has sought to diagnose what influence location has on the functional structure of small urban localities (of fewer than 20,000 inhabitants and typically called small towns). The work carried out has used two methods of functional classification based around either structural/hierarchical or morphological/functional analysis. The methodology of the classifications used is discussed in the next section of this paper. The location criterion was a consequence of location in regional space as well as transport accessibility of the different units of settlement in relation to large urban centres. Such an approach first allowed for the identification of 2 main categories of small town, i.e. those located within metropolitan areas (and thus in the vicinity of Poland's largest agglomerations), or else those located peripherally, i.e. out on the margins of regions, in areas in which access to more important centres is hindered for one reason or another. The hypothesis advanced from that was that towns in the first category are characterised by a specialised functional structure and linkage via socio-economic relationships that are stronger

in relation to key larger urban centres than the immediate vicinity; even as those in the second category are multi-functional in character and manifest strong relationships with the rural neighbourhood.

Methodological issues

The criterion used to distinguish towns and cities in Poland is legal/administrative in nature, with the number of people in the settlement unit not being important, while the possession of town rights in the legal context is. So it is that Poland's smallest town – Opatowiec – had just 338 inhabitants as of 2021, while Kozy, as the largest village, was home to as many as 12,744 people. However, this study's approach to the identification of "small towns" is based on the population criterion, even though this is seen to differ from country to country (typically in the range 5000-25,000 inhabitants). Thus, across the European Union (Dijkstra & Poelman, 2012; 2014) the situation can resemble that in Germany, where a small town has fewer than 50,000 inhabitants; even as France, Czechia and Poland generally consider a situation in which there are fewer than 20,000 people (Kwiatek-Sołtys & Mainet, 2014; Vaishar & Zapletalova, 2009). In the UK, the size interval is 7500-25,000 inhabitants while the typology deployed by the ESPON TOWN Project has small towns classed as those localities in the 5-25,000 size range (Servillo et al., 2017; ESPON, 2014).¹ In the present study, the arbitrary decision arrived at ultimately was that a small town is a settlement unit enjoying town rights and being home to fewer than 20,000 inhabitants.²

The work paid attention to two categories as regards location, involving: 1) small towns located in the direct range of impact of large urban centres (leaving these known for short as "metropolitan small towns"), or else 2) peripheral small towns in which a key feature is hindered access to the core centres regionally. The first group thus included towns located within selected metropolitan areas, where the spatial structure present in Poland identifies between 7 and 12 such metropolitan areas (Heffner, 2011; Smętkowski et al., 2008; Markowski & Marszał, 2006). However, the current "2030" Concept for the Country's Spatial Development (Koncepcja Przestrzennego Zagospodarowania Kraju 2030) – published in 2011 – suggests neither how many these areas are in number, nor within what boundaries they occur. In turn, the aforesaid ESPON (2007) project serving to identify so-called Functional Urban Areas and Metropolitan European Growth Areas within the EU Member States, suggests that Poland has 8 centres around which metropolitan areas have been taking shape.

¹ This project proceeded on the assumption that small and medium-sized towns (SMSTs) are localities with more than 5,000 inhabitants, present at a population density in excess of 300 people per km² but not qualifying as High-Density Urban Clusters. In practice, some of these localities are close to being small cities with even 50,000 inhabitants. And in European countries overall, localities meeting the criteria are home to 21% of the population (Atkinson, 2019).

² As of 2022, Poland had 964 territorial units enjoying town rights, with 739 having a population under 20,000. The country's administrative division provides for small towns enjoying a status as independent administrative units (of the so-called urban gmina type), or else representing just a part (in the case of the localities of the urban/rural gmina type).

Ultimately, then, to meet the needs of the work detailed here, a selection was made of 7 areas formed by the country's largest urban centres (i.e. Warsaw, Kraków, Katowice – within the Upper Silesian Conurbation, the Trójmiasto (Tri-City) of Gdańsk-Gdynia-Sopot, Poznań, Wrocław and Łódź). The cities are also all capitals of the Polish province-regions known as Voivodeships. The selection of metropolitan small towns took place on the basis of time taken to reach the main centre, which could not exceed 30 minutes. These criteria gave rise to a set of 46 towns, while the group of peripheral small towns – having been subject to a series of trial runs – was determined as including 45 centres located within the same 7 regions, but with the regional capitals not reachable by car in less than 90 minutes, and with a further criterion being that the journey time by car to a nearest urban centre of at least 100,000 inhabitants takes at least 60 minutes. Such defining circumstances ensure that the towns in this category are usually located on the edges of regions, far from the centres that make it possible for people to make use of higher-order services in education, health, culture, etc.

Figure 1– Location of the small towns selected for the study. A - small towns located in the direct range of impact of large urban centres; B - peripheral small towns. Source: Author.

The second methodological issue is the means of achieving the towns' functional classification. Two methods developed by the author were in fact used for this, one taking a morphological/functional approach, and the other a hierarchical/structural one. The former is based around 12 categories of land cover to be found within the administrative boundaries

of the urban localities under study. Poland's Baza Danych Obiektów Topograficznych at 1:10,000 scale (GUGiK, as accessed in January 2022) was used for this purpose, with the land-cover categories of interest being: 1) surface waters, 2) built-up areas, 3) forest land, 4) scrub, 5) areas under permanent cultivation, 6) grassy vegetation and agricultural grasslands, 7) land associated with transport, 8) waste ground, 9) squares, 10) landfills, 11) sites associated with the extraction of minerals and the disposal of spoil, and 12) other land not built on. On a more-detailed level, these categories include 35 sub-category types of land cover.

The morphological/functional classification of small towns applied two criteria based around four variables arising via the aggregation of the aforementioned land-use categories:

U – the area of urbanised land;

G – the area of green space;

R – the area of land serving residential needs;

I – the area of land serving industrial, including warehousing, needs.

Where the first criterion was concerned, each locality studied had a ratio value calculated for it whereby the area of green space (G) was set against the area of urbanised land (U). In the case of the second criterion, it was the area of land serving residential needs (R) that was compared with the area of land serving the needs of industry or warehousing (I). Values actually obtained were then compared with standard ones noted overall by reference to land use in the whole set of 722 small urban localities.³ Through this procedure of mathematical classification, it was possible to assign each locality to one of four categories characterised as follows:

1. housing estate towns (UR) are those with limited areas of greenspace as compared with urbanised land, as well as large areas devoted to residential functions as compared with those associated with industry;
2. industrial towns (UI) are those in which much more land is urbanised as opposed to covered in greenery, while the areas assigned to housing are limited in comparison with those assigned to industrial functions;
3. rest and recreation towns (GR) have extensive cover of greenspace compared with how much of the land has become urbanised, while simultaneously having proportionately large residential areas at the expense of industrial ones; and
4. towns displaying dichotomy (GI) are those with plenty of greenspace as compared with urbanised areas, even as industrial land prevails over residential.

³ It should be noted that the method of classifying small cities was performed in earlier studies on the basis of the entire set of small cities in 2019. However, the analysis of the relationship of small cities with central regional centres was performed on a set of 91 selected small cities (as explained in the text of the study).

Figure 2 – Conceptualisation of the morphological classification of small urban centres. Source: own research

Where morphological/functional classification is engaged in, the results are going to be very much determined by the territorial extents of city limits. For there are examples of small urban centres of a compact nature, whose boundaries are set at such a distance that the area within them is first and foremost built up. On the other hand, there are localities of rather large area, whose boundaries extend well out into land that is clearly rural in character, including as they do so large areas of both farmland and forest. Nevertheless, areas of the latter type may well have only a small group of inhabitants residing – and carrying out activity in – the said areas of a typically rural nature. While these differences do exist, we may assume that the number and regional spread of localities under study (in the two categories) sufficed to leave the final outcome of the work influenced to only a limited degree.

Category of territorial unit	Average population	Average area (ha)
Small town	6,702	1,446.5
Municipality	15,307	12,624.6
Rural municipality	7,083	12,506.1
Urban-rural municipality	13,759	16,571.8
Municipality with small town	12,161	14,362.9

Table 1 – Average area (ha) and number of inhabitants of small towns in comparison with basic categories of municipalities in Poland, 2021. Source: Author's own elaboration based on data from Central Statistical Office.

The second method of classification entails analysis of the relationship pertaining between urban centres and their surroundings, as well as the branch structure characterising enterprises operating within the given settlement units. The assumption here is that the relationships may have a profile that is either local or beyond the local (supra-local), as a reflection of a given locality's position in hierarchies of different kinds (be they administrative, economic, educational, commercial, or whatever). Ultimately, a hierarchical part-

classification was devised that sought to reflect this diversity through adoption of variables as follows:

1. administrative status,
2. numbers of public-sector business entities,
3. numbers of people commuting to work in the city.

In relation to each of these three variables, threshold values were then adopted to allow a given urban centre to be assigned to the categories serving local (L) or supra-local (C) functions in respect of surrounding areas. The ultimate assumption was then that the serving of functions above and beyond the purely local is indicated by: 1) the status of seat of the powiat- (county-) level authority known as the *starostwo* (office of the person in the leadership post of *starosta*).⁴ 2) an above-average number of public-sector entities, and 3) an above-average number of people commuting to work in the urban centre of the aforementioned profile. It was further assumed that a town might be involved with functions beyond the local where any of the above three conditions is met. Equally, all remaining localities were deemed to have local functions only.

In analysing the role of different component elements of the branch structure when it comes to enterprises located in small urban localities, it is possible to draw a distinction between two main groups, i.e. towns characterised by a specialised structure (S), in which one of its elements prevails (for example allowing us to refer to “industrial town”, “tourist centre”, etc.), or in which the structure is seen to comprise many branches (M). Identification of these two groups was based around the two following variables:

1. the numbers of registered business entities employing at least 250 people;
2. the numbers of registered business entities included within the 2 out of 21 Sections of Polska Klasyfikacja Gospodarcza (PKD, or Polish Economic Classification) that are best represented overall.

In the case of each variable threshold values was set precisely, with this allowing for the identification of a subset of small urban centre characterized by a specialised economic structure. It was recognised (albeit rather arbitrarily) that such a structure is indicated by the presence in a town of this kind of at least one large business entity (employing at least 250 people), as well as a circumstance in which a majority of such entities registered are from one or the other of the aforementioned key PKD sectors. That said, a locality under study might be recognised as a town of specialised economic structure where it meets either of the two aforesaid conditions.

⁴ The powiat is one of Poland’s units of territorial administration, roughly comparable with that of other countries’ counties. The regional/provincial unit above it in the hierarchy is the voivodeship (województwo) – of which there are 16, while below it there is the local-authority gmina (2,477 in number). The number of units in Poland with the powiat designation is 314, though there are 66 urban localities that also enjoy this official status.

Ultimately, the possibility arising from this was to draw distinctions between 4 different categories of towns:

- localities characterised by functions beyond the local in which the economic structure is specialised (CS);
- localities characterised by functions beyond the local in which the economic structure is of a multi-branched nature (CM);
- localities characterised by purely local functions but featuring a specialised economic structure (LS); and
- localities again of local functions but featuring a multi-branched economic structure (LM).

(L) Local centres	(M) Multi-branch structure		(C) Supra-local centres
	(LM) centres of local functions and a multi-branched economic structure	(CM) centres of supra-local functions and a multi-branched economic structure	
	(LS) centres of local functions and a specialised economic structure	(CS) centres of supra-local functions and a specialised economic structure	
	(S) Specialised structure		

Figure 3 – Conceptualisation of the hierarchical/structural classification. Source: Author.

Presentation, interpretation and discussion of results

Since 1989, the small urban centres of Poland have undergone considerable change. In the first place, rapid economic development in areas close to large cities has taken place, as accompanied by dynamic development of single-family housing construction. In the second place, financial support via EU funding has ensured a transformation of the transport infrastructure, with the result that accessibility has improved greatly. In the third place, many new business entities have made their appearance and ensured a reshaping of the economic structure. And in the fourth place, the inhabitants of the localities under study have tended to engage in a process of building civil society, in which levels of activeness in the community have risen. These are just selected examples of positive change arising out of economic transformation, though it has to be said that a number of negative processes have also arisen – linked to the migratory outflow from peripheral areas, ageing of the population in small urban localities, chaotic planning and physical development, excessive burdening of the transport network thanks to burgeoning numbers of private cars, growing poverty, and an intensification of certain social ills (Bartosiewicz et al., 2019; Krzysztofik, 2019; Łobodzińska,

2016). All of these phenomena have also been exerting their effects on the shaping of functional structure, and on increasing spatial differentiation, markedly in the direction of disparity.

As any comparison is made between structure in the 2 analysed categories of locality – i.e. small metropolitan towns and small peripheral towns – it has to be conceded that the distribution of the different morphological and functional classes within that structure proves differentiated to a marked degree. Thus, the set of peripheral urban localities shows a balanced distribution across the four-class structure devised, even as the housing estate town and industrial town categories are the ones found to prevail among the metropolitan localities. The major share accounted for by Class 1 (with almost half of all the metropolitan units analysed) just serves to confirm the widely-known fact that the residential function is here among the key socioeconomic functions served.

In the case of most of the small towns located close to others of a “central” status and designation, the period since the mid-1990s has been associated with the aforesaid dynamic development of single-family housing construction (Zborowski & Raźniak, 2013). This phenomenon has brought others along with it, mostly threats associated with precipitate and precocious development, spatial chaos, growing pressure on the natural environment, and indeed the degradation and/or fragmentation of natural habitats. The abrupt and huge expansion of the built-up areas has also of course changed the architectural characteristics and spatial layout that was present before in what were previously small towns or even rural settlements more in the nature of villages (Bański, 2020). Effects have arisen out of both the concentration of new building, and its dispersal over wider areas. Transport difficulties have mostly grown, thanks to the dynamic development of the residential function and associated huge increase in numbers of cars. Somewhat paradoxically, the very access to the urban localities enjoying “central” status that was the attraction in the first place is now being very much hindered by a transport system that has failed to adjust to the new circumstances. Times taken to arrive at work or school have risen.

The author’s 2014 research carried out among 38 representatives of local government or else those co-working with them via institutions located within the Metropolitan Area of Poland’s Tri-City (of Gdańsk-Gdynia-Sopot) gave commutes to work as the key factor conditioning the development of small towns and rural areas alike.⁵ This matter was pointed to by 27 of those interviewed. Lower down the hierarchy, the further factors of the development of tourist services and of private enterprise were mentioned by 18 and 15 respondents respectively. Thanks to a large number of new road and rail developments, Poland’s small towns now (again) often have somewhat improved access to central localities.

⁵ The work was done to meet needs as the “Strategy for the Development of the Gdańsk Metropolitan Area through to 2030” was being drawn up. The expert report devised was entitled *Rola małych miast i obszarów wiejskich w rozwoju obszaru metropolitalnego*. A synthesis is at: https://www.metropoliagdansk.pl/upload/files/5_D_rozwojmalychmiast.pdf (accessed 23.12.2022).

However, the situation remains far from ideal, and indeed continues to pose a key challenge where the development of metropolitan areas is concerned.

The growth in the importance of metropolitan towns' residential functions has meant changes in population structure. New housing estates have attracted an influx of well-educated, better-off people, whose "demands" are also greater. An effect has been to spur on the development of services, commerce and infrastructure. The stream of migrants of productive age was drawn to small towns by the relatively cheap land available to build on or run a business from, the lower rates charged for municipal services, and a supportive attitude towards entrepreneurship being manifested by local authorities (Śleszyński, 2009). Where the peripheral urban centres are concerned, the dynamic development began sooner (even during the communist era), thanks to new industrial and construction-related developments. This was, among other things, the result of policies contained in sectoral strategies and the country's spatial development concept.⁶ The people reaching the smaller towns at that time were of rural origin, and they mainly found employment in plants and factories where work did not demand special qualifications. Post-1989, the peripheral towns suffered stagnation, even with population decline a phenomenon observed frequently.

Indeed, in the last decade, a decided majority of Poland's small towns have been experiencing demographic change of a negative nature, thanks to both natural loss of population and outflows due to migration. The effect overall has been for populations to age (Bański et al., 2021). The migratory processes are proving more significant, and their intensification is indicated and documented in the subject literature (for many countries), with the phenomenon seen as a crisis affecting individual areas and indeed whole regions (Hoekveld, 2012; Haase et al., 2016; Pirisi & Trócsányi, 2014). Unsurprisingly peripheral towns have been particularly affected by this phenomenon, and – as it is first and foremost young people who migrate, including especially women – this obviously denotes localities subject to present or future negative influences of both an economic and social nature. For the ageing of society ensures intensive erosion of the quality of labour-force resources and social capital. Another negative consequence is a reduction in levels of demand for goods and services, with a knock-on effect in limiting entrepreneurship and the degree to which advantage is taken of social and economic infrastructure, even as closure of "unneeded" businesses and institutions is favoured. Such a situation again translates into reduced demand for new employment, and hence to an increase in levels of unemployment that induce a further wave of migration. Any breaking of this vicious circle then represents a major challenge for local authorities.

⁶ We refer here to two documents: Plan przestrzennego zagospodarowania kraju do roku 1990 (*A Plan for the Country's Spatial Management up to the Year 1990*, 1974, Biuletyn KPZK PAN 85, Warsaw); and Strategia uprzemysłowienia a proces urbanizacji (*Industrialisation strategies and the urbanisation process*, 1982, Biuletyn KPZK PAN 119, Warsaw).

Research taking in the 2010–2017 period reveals that, from among 670 small urban localities in Poland that were analysed, just 10 feature an age structure among inhabitants that is actually rejuvenating. And among these, 5 are located in the immediate vicinity of large cities (Bański et al., 2021).⁷ These localities are being arrived at by young people or young families, from both regional centres and rural areas (Zborowski & Raźniak, 2013), drawn by a cost of living that is potentially lower than in the city, even as living conditions seem better in many obvious ways. The remaining 5 localities referred to in which the ageing of the population has been reversed are urban localities serving spa/health resort, industrial, or transport-related functions. In these cases, the “magnets” for young people appear to be a good range of job opportunities on the labour market, as well as road connections with large cities that continue to favour commuting.

Figure 4 – The morphological and functional structure of the studied small urban localities within metropolitan areas (A) or peripheral areas (B), where UR denotes the so-called housing estate towns, UI industrial towns, GR R&R towns and GI towns characterised by dichotomy. Source: Author.

In comparison with the peripheral areas, the metropolitan areas feature a greater share of towns of the industrial class (respectively 37% compared with 27%). These are centres in which large industrial plants once operated but have mostly been restructured into a series of smaller entities, often with these entering into further cooperation with the industrial or construction sectors as present in nearby central localities. For certain branches of industry may be located in the vicinity (albeit beyond the administrative limits) of large cities, perhaps as a reflection of the burden a given plant is capable of imposing on the natural environment, and/or the demands for large areas of land already enjoying designations relating to industry or warehousing. The rather smaller share of localities with an industrial function that characterises the functional structure of peripheral towns reflects the way in which the collapse of the communist system unleashed a period of economic transformation that resulted

⁷ The remaining 660 localities featured differing degrees of population ageing.

in plant closures (or divide-ups) in many towns. Beyond that, there is the fact that the structure of peripheral localities is characterised by a rather high share of towns characterised by dichotomy, within which industrial functions often have a very significant role to play.

Industrial towns remain a characteristic element of Poland's settlement network, even though they are very largely a product of the communist era. The idea then was to achieve as even a development of all regions of the country as possible, *inter alia* by way of the redevelopment or *de novo* location of factories, works and plants. The aim of even distribution of industry across Poland might even mean locations in small administrative units. A further objective of the new development of industry was to attract in inhabitants from overpopulated rural areas. As of the 1950-1970 period, the share of the entire population accounted for by urban dwellers rose from 39% to above 52% (Bański, 2007). At the same time, while priority continued to be attached to heavy industry, there began a decline in the share of overall investment outlays going on the old industrial districts, to the benefit of new centres of industry much more dispersed in nature (Lijewski, 1993).

In the 1970s, change in Poland's ruling elite signalled greater outlays on industry, and the beginning of a process of constructing large new industrial plants on the basis of credit extended from abroad. It was then that new industrial developments came to be spread most widely across the country. The plan for the development of the settlement network was in turn based on the so-called moderate polycentric concentration. The main strategic aim was to shift part of Poland's industrial potential from the south to the north and east. And it was in small urban localities in particular that industry was to develop. Economic crisis partly thwarted the ambitious goals, but the communist-era policy did nevertheless result in the appearance of a relatively large group of small industrial centres, which were indeed at times located far from large agglomerations and industrial districts *per se*. The development of plants and factories in small towns obviously attracted new inhabitants, in particular from surrounding rural areas. Indeed, some commuted in to work on a daily basis, while others migrated in a more permanent way to the towns. A still-visible feature of the 1970s and 1980s was thus an abrupt development of multi-family block housing thrown up to house the new influx of population in what had been small centres rather resembling country towns.

When Poland made its more-recent socio-economic transformation out of communism and central planning, the small towns underwent dynamic change in their employment structures. This is the case in small peripheral towns that had hitherto assigned a major role to the industrial function, factory closures and restructurings took place, with often-drastic effects given that these had typically become the given towns' main places of employment. Crises on local labour markets ensued, with unemployment soaring, and having the knock-on effect of promoting out-migration of inhabitants (Kantor-Pietraga et al., 2012). As has been noted, it was first and foremost jobs in industry that were lost, with employment in the (non-market or market) services increasing in significance. Nevertheless, population loss

continued, in particular among people of productive age; with the knock-on effects from that including loss of income in many towns. The economic problems were naturally overlain by social ones (unemployment, social exclusion, social ills, etc.), as well as an overriding lack of interest shown by potential investors wherever locations could be regarded as peripheral (given a greater degree of separation from key regional centres or main routes of communication) (Domański & Nowról, 2010; Kamińska & Mularczyk, 2014).

The structure associated with the towns in peripheral locations is found to feature a large share of localities in the R&R or dichotomous classes. The feature common to both is the large share of green space within the town limits, in part because the boundaries present have often been fixed well beyond the core built-up areas. This has meant inclusion of large areas of forest, but also other greenspace in parks and squares, and scrub or shrubbery. The so-called towns characterised by dichotomy earn this name because they have large “industrial” areas (actually mainly involving the warehousing sub-category), given a main function of serving the farming sector locally. It is after all typical for the peripheral small towns to be surrounded by rural areas that tend to be relatively monofunctional, given the major prevalence of agriculture.

Type	Metropolitan localities	Peripheral localities
Centres serving local functions	30	62
Centres serving functions beyond the local	70	38
Centres of specialised economic structure	57	42
Centres with a multi-branch structure	43	58

Table 2 – Percentage shares of studied categories of small urban centre accounted for by different hierarchical and structural classes. Source: Author.

Where the hierarchical/structural classification was concerned, the breakdown into particular classes within the structuring of small urban localities points clearly roles played in regional and local social and economic space. Results of the analysis confirm generalised conclusions arising out of the morphological/functional classification referred to previously. What are first and foremost involved here are more economically-specialised metropolitan towns whose social and economic roles extend into a zone beyond their immediate vicinity. The largest group (accounting for around 50% of all localities studied) comprises towns with functions going beyond the purely local (i.e. supra-local), in which economic structure is specialised. These areas usually play host to large business entities in a position to shape the economic specifics of given localities. Similar results have in fact arisen out of research carried out in Poland’s core Mazovia region, in which the two groups of towns analysed were either of the agglomeration type (as exemplified by Pilawa, Serock, Radzymin and Ożarów Mazowiecki, and located in the immediate vicinity of Warsaw) or peripheral (like Łosice, Chorzele, Różan,

Lipsko and Przysuch), in the sense that they are located on the margins of the given region (Bański et al., 2016). The agglomeration towns differ from the peripheral one in their greater shares of business entities operating in industrial production, construction, the R&D sector or market services. Public services are only of lesser importance here, given that they may be rendered in part by a more major centre (as would be the case with education, culture and certain healthcare services). In contrast, peripheral towns have a higher share of entities in the sectors of trade, transport, education, health and other non-market services (which is to say activities important, not only for inhabitants of a town, but also for those who live in a given locality's immediate vicinity).

Figure 5 – Small towns in metropolitan (A) and peripheral (B) areas classified using the hierarchical/structural method; where CS denotes centres discharging functions beyond the purely local and featuring a specialised economic structure, CM centres whose functions are likewise “supra-local” in which the economic structure is multi-branched, LS centres with local functions and a specialised economic structure, and LM centres with local functions and a multi-branched economic structure. Source: Author.

The hierarchical/structural analysis shows how more than 40% of all peripheral towns are of a multi-functional nature, and closely linked with the rural areas tending to surround these on all sides. These are then places in which local administrative, educational, service-related and residential functions are served. When set against those in the metropolitan category, peripheral centres appear to be more balanced in terms of their business structure. This probably reflects the different role units in peripheral areas play vis-à-vis the rural areas that surround them. Alongside the productive function, they have a key importance where social, service-related, commercial and communications-related services are concerned. The peripheral towns concentrate non-market services as well as diverse manifestations of cultural life. In contrast, the metropolitan towns feature de facto ceding of some of their functions (in healthcare, finance, education and transport) to a more major metropolitan centre in the vicinity, this in particular where the people residing in rural areas are concerned.

Conclusions

The work presented here has been concerned with two categories of urban centre differing in terms of the location within defined territorial structure as well as transport accessibility vis-à-vis the localities enjoying “central” status in the regional context. The results confirmed a priori assumptions regarding differentiation of the socio-economic functions of small urban localities in line with their locations. Thus, centres located within metropolitan areas enjoying a good level of transport accessibility are first and foremost likely to serve residential and/or industrial functions (albeit with it needing to be stressed that the concept of “industry” here denotes all productive branches, as well as warehousing, institutions in R&D, etc.). Within the morphological and functional structure, the greatest numbers of towns are in this category. The high share accounted for by industrial centres reflects economic relationships pertaining between the small towns and the localities serving centre-related functions. The largest group of small metropolitan towns comprises those serving functions above and beyond the purely local, and characterised by the possession of a specialised economic structure. In turn, the differentiation of peripherally-located towns from the point of view of their morphological and functional structure is greater, making it harder to point to a dominant class (given that all four classes of urban centre identified are found to be characterised by similar abundances).

Differences between metropolitan and peripheral towns prove to be more of a reflection of the hierarchy (role in a region’s socioeconomic space) than they are of economic structure. Results from hierarchical/structural analysis make it clear that a decided majority of peripheral towns are centres serving local functions and characterised by multi-branch economic structure – in which an important role is also played by non-market services. Towns of this kind play their key part in servicing the inhabitants of local villages – as regards services as such, but also education and commerce. At the same time, this denotes that small peripheral towns play far more important functions for the rural areas around them than do small towns of a metropolitan character. Moreover, they often represent the only alternative when it comes to finding work, attending school or availing of services. In turn, small metropolitan towns (being located close to major regional centres) are characterised by much more limited competitiveness when it comes to functions discharged to the benefit of surrounding areas.

Regional policy usually sees a large agglomeration as a centre of socio-economic and cultural growth capable of sending out development impulses into the areas surrounding it. Those environs, including the small towns located there, have human resources and represent a particular kind of hinterland of development in relation to the main centre. They supply resources of labour, sometimes raw materials and food, and/or represent places in which rest and recreation can be taken. However, such an approach (if adhered to) may in fact encourage spatial polarisation of a region, whereby functional linkage pertaining between small towns and a larger central place will mainly be one-way in nature. To prevent that negative phenomenon of monocentric development from gathering pace, it is indicated for mechanisms

to be put in place to ensure and facilitate a (re)distribution of some profits and benefits gained in the centres of development to areas in their hinterlands, with effort also being made to shape the relationships pertaining between one small(er) urban locality and another. As this is all being done, it is important to recognise the specific functional features of given towns, noting the way in which this awareness will help ensure the proper and better shaping of the relationships referred to.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no competing interests.

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